

THE MEANING OF CHRIST'S RESURRECTION IN CHRISTUS VIVIT AS A SOURCE OF HOPE FOR YOUNG CATHOLIC PEOPLE

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Abstract

This research explores the meaning of the Resurrection of Christ in the Apostolic Exhortation *Christus Vivit* and its relevance as a source of hope for Catholic youth in the midst of contemporary challenges. In an era marked by rapid technological development, cultural shifts, and a growing crisis of identity, many young Catholics struggle with spiritual disorientation, weakened faith, and a sense of detachment from the Church. *Christus Vivit*, issued by Pope Francis, affirms that the living and risen Christ accompanying young people, renew their lives, and strengthens them to face their struggles with courage and hope. This study aims to explain the core messages of *Christus Vivit*, analyze the theological meaning of Christ's Resurrection within the document, and demonstrate how the Resurrection becomes a concrete source of hope for young Catholics. Employing a library research method, the study draws on Sacred Scripture, the Catechism of Catholic Church, conciliar documents such as *Lumen Gentium* and *Dei Verbum*, as well as theological literature and pastoral writings. The data are analyzed using a descriptive theological approach to synthesize key themes related to resurrection, hope, and youth spirituality. The findings show that Christ's Resurrection is not merely a historical event but a living reality that empowers young People to rise from discouragement, rediscover their identity as beloved children of God, and actively participate in the renewal of the Church. The study concludes that the Resurrection of Christ, as presented in *Christus Vivit*, serves as a profound foundation of hope for Catholic youth, while the Church is called to accompany them with love, openness, and pastoral creativity so that they may become joyful witnesses of the risen Christ in today's world.

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**Related declarations are provided in the final section of this article.

I. Introduction

The Resurrection of Christ is at the heart of the Church's proclamation and the foundation of Christian faith. Without the Resurrection, faith has no meaning, as affirmed in 1 Corinthians 15:14. The Resurrection of Christ, in the context of Catholic youth, provides a new direction for understanding life, suffering, and hope. Pope Francis' Apostolic Exhortation *Christus Vivit* affirms that Christ is alive and desires that every young person live in the abundance of God's love (*Christus Vivit*, art. 1:7). The risen Christ is a source of strength, renewal, and joy, especially for young Catholics searching for identity and meaning in a fast-paced and stressful world.

Young Catholics face various challenges such as identity crises, emotional instability, the pressures of digital culture, and moral struggles that often weaken their zest for life (Pratama, Firmanto, & Aluwesia, 2021). The Church, through *Christus Vivit*, affirms that Catholic youth are God's present, not merely the Church's future (*Christus Vivit*, art. 64:26). Thus, mentoring young Catholics is a crucial concern for the Church, enabling them to experience the living and risen Christ.

This study aims to explain the meaning of Christ's resurrection in *Christus Vivit* and its relevance as a source of hope for young Catholics. The study employed a library research method, examining Church documents and theological literature. The focus of this study is to discover how Christ's resurrection is understood in *Christus Vivit* and how the Church can foster hope in young people through pastoral care rooted in the resurrection.

II. Discussion: Theoretical Study

A. Christ's Resurrection in Church Tradition

Christ's resurrection is the culmination of Christian faith and the foundation of human salvation. The Catechism of the Catholic Church (CCC art. 638:196) states that the resurrection is a truth that has been central to the Church's proclamation since the beginning of its tradition. Christ's resurrection is understood as God's act of raising Jesus and giving new life to all humanity. This truth is not only a historical event, but also a reality of faith that has been lived out by the Church throughout the ages (Malingkas & Roni, 2024). Through the resurrection, God affirms His victory over sin and death, while simultaneously opening the way to new life for humanity.

Scripture depicts the resurrection as a reality that transformed the disciples from fearful to courageous preachers (cf. John 20:19). Young figures such as Joseph, Samuel, David, and Solomon exemplify how God calls young people to great works in the history of salvation. Church tradition affirms that the resurrection is not only a milestone in the history of salvation, but also an experience of faith that renews and revitalizes the Church.

As a living reality of faith, the resurrection is not only understood at the doctrinal level but also impacts the spiritual lives of believers. The resurrection strengthens humanity in the face of suffering, points us toward eternal life, and helps us interpret the cross in the light of hope.

The meaning of the resurrection affirms that faith does not end with death but finds its fulfillment in new life with God. Faith in the resurrection is at the heart of the Church's liturgy, especially during the celebration of Easter, where the Church glorifies Christ who conquered death (Pondaag & Pinedendi, 2023). Thus, Christ's resurrection is a source of joy, a foundation of hope, and a spiritual energy that enables believers to live in love and fidelity to God.

B. Catholic Youth in Christus Vivit

Christus Vivit pays close attention to the conditions of young Catholics living in the dynamics of the modern era. Pope Francis describes young people as individuals full of potential, creativity, and hope, yet also vulnerable to identity crises and cultural pressures (Christus Vivit, Art. 264:99). Young people are seen as a vital part of the Church, called to take an active role in the proclamation of the Gospel and the renewal of the Church. Within the context of faith, young people are invited to experience a personal encounter with Christ as a friend and guide in life.

The Church emphasizes the importance of pastoral care oriented toward dialogue, engagement, and a presence that reflects Christ's love. Young Catholics feel that the Church is no longer relevant to their lives, when in fact, the Church is present to be a place of guidance and strength amidst the challenges of the times (Simanjuntak & Bangun, 2023). Young people need care that is personal, liberating, and relevant to the world of young Catholics. Therefore, Christus Vivit emphasizes that the Church must be present as a community that listens, embraces, and entrusts the task of service to young Catholics (Christus Vivit, Art. 235:89).

Young Catholics are not merely recipients of the message but active subjects of Church renewal, for Jesus himself appears as a young person and serves as an inspiration to young Catholics. Young people rooted in Christ possess steadfastness and a clear direction in life, as well as the ability to be messengers of love in society. The Church therefore views young Catholics as signs of new life; their energy, hope, and creativity enable the Church to continue to be renewed and remain relevant in the modern world (Tawa, Meja, & Yogalianti, 2021).

C. Christian Hope from the Perspective of the Resurrection.

Hope is a crucial dimension of Christian life. The Catechism of the Catholic Church (art. 1817:480) affirms that hope is the belief that God is faithful to His promises and gives eternal life to His people. Pope Benedict XVI emphasized that hope is not mere optimism, but a profound conviction that God accompanies humans in every step of their lives (Spe Salvi, art. 31:38). Christ's resurrection is the foundation of all Christian hope, for in the resurrection, God proves that death does not have ultimate power.

This hope becomes especially relevant when young Catholics face crises, suffering, or inner struggles. The Apostolic Exhortation Christus Vivit affirms that the risen Christ gives us the strength to rise above adversity and look to the future with hope (Christus Vivit, art. 119:46). Thus, Christ's resurrection becomes the spiritual foundation that enables young Catholics to persevere and grow in faith.

Christian hope not only provides a direction toward eternal salvation but also shapes how people face the realities of everyday life. Hope empowers young Catholics to persevere through the inner struggles and pressures of the modern age, for Christ's resurrection is proof that God's promises never fail and His love is unfailing. Thus, hope is not merely an eschatological vision, but a life-giving force that strengthens human progress in the process of repentance, purification of faith, and moral struggle. The belief that Christ is risen provides the assurance that the future is in God's hands, enabling young Catholics to move forward without fear, to face life with gratitude, and to understand suffering as part of the process toward a new life with Him.

III. Research Methodology

This research uses a library research approach, as explained in the document. The research was conducted by examining various literature, Church documents, the Bible, and other supporting sources to obtain a theological foundation and conceptual understanding of the meaning of Christ's resurrection and its relevance for young Catholics (Sari & Asmendri, 2020). This method was chosen because the research theme focuses on the analysis of Church documents, particularly *Christus Vivit*, *Spe Salvi*, *Dei Verbum*, *Lumen Gentium*, the Bible, and the Catechism of the Catholic Church. Library research is a theoretical study, reference work, and other scholarly literature related to the culture, values, and norms that develop in the social situation being studied (Sugiyono, 2013).

Library research allows researchers to collect theological, doctrinal, and pastoral data through the review of authoritative written sources. Zed (2008) explains that library research is conducted by examining expert opinions and written sources to gain an in-depth understanding of the research problem. In this context, the research process was conducted through the following stages: (1) problem identification, (2) collection of primary and secondary sources, (3) critical reading of the *Christus Vivit* document, (4) theological analysis of the theme of the resurrection, and (5) drawing conclusions based on a synthesis of the findings.

Data collection techniques were conducted through documentation, namely collecting data in the form of Church documents, theological books, scientific articles, journals, previous research results, as well as the Holy Scriptures and the Catechism of the Catholic Church relevant to the research theme. The research instrument was the researcher's ability to conduct critical and systematic textual analysis, so that the meaning of Christ's resurrection and its implications could be accurately explained within the context of *Christus Vivit*.

All sources used in this research are valid and authoritative, particularly the Apostolic Exhortation *Christus Vivit* as the primary source. Through this library research method, the researcher was able to gain a comprehensive understanding of the meaning of Christ's resurrection and how the Church interprets it as a source of hope for young Catholics today.

IV. Research Findings

The Meaning of Christ's Resurrection in *Christus Vivit* as a Source of Hope for Young Catholics. The Resurrection of Christ in *Christus Vivit* is understood as a reality that enlivens the

Church and empowers young Catholics to live their lives in light of Christ's resurrection. Pope Francis states that the living Christ provides new spirit, new hope, and a clear direction for young Catholics (Christus Vivit, Art. 1:7). The Resurrection is seen as God's work that restores and transforms human life, especially when people experience doubt or despair. The Resurrection of Christ in Christus Vivit is depicted not merely as a Church dogma but as a living reality that provides transformative power for humanity, especially young Catholics. Pope Francis affirms that Christ lives, accompanies, and walks with young Catholics in the struggles of life. The Resurrection is not merely a historical event, but a force that continues to operate in the life of the church today.

The Resurrection of Christ is a source of strength for young Catholics to rise above various forms of suffering and weakness. The hope born of the Resurrection provides real motivation for young people to face a rapidly changing and demanding world. Pope Francis emphasizes that Christ never abandons young people in difficult situations, but is always present as a friend who strengthens and guides young Catholics (Christus Vivit, art. 35:18). Christ's Resurrection provides a spiritual foundation for young Catholics to resist the temptations of discouragement. Christ is a friend who not only sets an example but also strengthens them along the journey. Christ's Resurrection signifies that Christ remains alive and accompanies every journey of young Catholics. The Apostolic Exhortation Christus Vivit serves as a bridge connecting faith with the psychological realities of young Catholics, so that the Resurrection is understood not only as a truth of faith but as an experience of inner healing.

Christ's Resurrection is understood as an invitation for young Catholics to renew their lives, abandon sin, and embark on a new journey with Christ. The Apostolic Exhortation Christus Vivit emphasizes that every young Catholic is called to live in the peace, joy, and hope that flow from the risen Christ (Christus Vivit, art. 119:46). This serves as the foundation for the Church in designing pastoral care that leads young Catholics to an authentic experience of faith. This hope creates space for personal transformation, namely, changes in thinking, moral choices, relationships with others, and life orientation. Christ's resurrection affirms that failure is not the end, but a new beginning with Christ, who greets us with peace.

The Resurrection of Christ reminds us that young Catholics have dignity and a role in the life of the Church. The Church views young Catholics not as objects of formation, but as subjects of proclamation and witnesses of Christ's resurrection in the modern world (Christus Vivit, Art. 64:26). Young Catholics are given a direct role in church life through their creativity, energy, and vibrant spirituality. The Church believes that young Catholics have the ability to renew the body of the Church, not merely replacing it in the future but also playing a role in the present. This affirms that the resurrection empowers young Catholics to engage in the renewal of the Church as living witnesses of the faith.

The Resurrection of Christ, in the pastoral dynamic, presents a new pattern of accompaniment. Accompaniment is no longer merely teaching, but also accompanies, provides space for dialogue, and listens. This research appears to provide an understanding that the Church needs to provide a platform for young Catholics to express themselves, determine their

direction in life, and participate in the mission of evangelization. This approach not only makes the Church more relevant to young Catholics but also revitalizes the Church itself. The Resurrection of Christ provides a foundation for the Church to entrust a role to young Catholics, with the awareness that the Holy Spirit works through them.

The Resurrection of Christ also serves as a foundation of hope that guides young Catholics in facing the challenges of our time. A world filled with uncertainty, a competitive culture, and emotional pressures make young Catholics vulnerable to despair. The Apostolic Exhortation *Christus Vivit* affirms that Christ's Resurrection assures that "there is no wound that God's love cannot heal" (*Christus Vivit*, Art. 119:46). Christ's Resurrection is a source of spiritual strength that guides young Catholics toward maturity in the faith.

The Resurrection of Christ in *Christus Vivit* also affirms the personal relationship between Christ and young Catholics as a living and dynamic one. The risen Christ does not appear as a distant or abstract figure, but as a person who knows the inner struggles of young people, listens to their anxieties, and addresses them with healing love. This relationship provides a spiritual foundation that enables young Catholics to build spiritual confidence, accept themselves as they are, and find the courage to move forward. Christ's Resurrection, thus, fosters an awareness that Christian faith is not a moral burden, but rather a liberating and strengthening encounter for young Catholics on their journey.

Beyond its personal impact, this research demonstrates that Christ's resurrection has social and missionary consequences. Young Catholics who experience the resurrection are called to be witnesses in the world. Young Catholics not only receive the faith but also share it. The Church positions young Catholics as living messengers, bringing the light of Christ to a world thirsting for hope. The resurrection of Christ is not merely a faith to be believed, but also a mission to be carried out. Young Catholics are invited to be agents of love, peacemakers, and agents of social transformation.

This research confirms that Christ's resurrection has concrete pastoral power and broad impact. The Church is called to develop faith formation programs based on the spirituality of the resurrection, namely dialogical accompaniment, participatory empowerment, and contextual faith formation. If the Church faithfully provides space for young Catholics to participate, the resurrection will not only be understood but also experienced and lived. The Church will become a young, dynamic, joyful Church, continually renewed by the power of the resurrection.

The resurrection of Christ is understood as the work of the Holy Spirit who continually renews the Church. The Spirit who raised Christ is the same Spirit who moves young Catholics to be witnesses of love and bearers of hope in the world (*Christus Vivit*, Art. 35:18). Thus, the Holy Spirit works through the resurrection to guide the Church and young Catholics to a life of holiness and love. The resurrection of Christ presents a hopeful paradigm of faith for young Catholics. The resurrection of Christ also gives them the courage to look to the future with spiritual optimism, not empty optimism. Young Catholics learn to live in faithfulness, perseverance, and service. The resurrection of Christ becomes a source of strength to fight pessimism, rise from their falls, and continue walking with the risen Christ. This research shows

that the resurrection of Christ is central to the spiritual identity of young Catholics, representing both the present and the future of the Church.

Furthermore, the resurrection of Christ, from the perspective of *Christus Vivit*, provides a new orientation for the Church's understanding of the faith growth process of young Catholics. The Church is encouraged not to impose a uniform model of faith, but rather to appreciate the diverse processes, rhythms, and contexts of young Catholics' lives. The resurrection of Christ serves as a pedagogical principle of faith that emphasizes patience, hope, and trust in the work of the Holy Spirit within young Catholics. With this approach, the Church not only maintains the purity of the teachings of the faith but also presents a welcoming, open Church capable of becoming a spiritual home for young Catholics searching for meaning in life.

Ultimately, the resurrection of Christ affirms that the faith journey of young Catholics is one that is always open to renewal. Young Catholics are called to continue growing, learning from failure, and daring to begin again with the risen Christ. The resurrection guarantees that the life of faith does not stop at human weakness but is always directed toward new possibilities in God's love. Rooted in the resurrection of Christ, young Catholics are strengthened to live as individuals of hope, faithfulness, and responsibility, while also being a sign of the Church's living and relevant presence in a constantly changing world.

V. Conclusion

The Resurrection of Christ in *Christus Vivit* is understood as the center of faith and a source of hope that renews the lives of young Catholics. It empowers young Catholics to rise above adversity, affirms their dignity, and invites them to actively participate in the life of the Church. The Apostolic Exhortation *Christus Vivit* affirms that the living Christ always accompanies young Catholics and provides clear direction for their journey of faith. Thus, the Resurrection forms the basis for the Church's relevant and compassionate pastoral care for young Catholics.

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